

ADVANTAGES OF USING INTERACTIVE PEDAGOGICAL SOFTWARE TOOLS IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the article, the fundamental changes taking place in our society, practical actions regarding the step-by-step transition to an information society, and the wide-ranging reforms being carried out regarding integration into the global education system, the wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process, iSpring Quizmaker 8 Information about the program options is provided.

Key words: Information society, iSpring Quizmaker program, test, mixed test, electronic course.

The state of development of information and communication technologies depends primarily on the intellectual potential of society, including the development of the education sector. Issues of the content and quality of education are considered a priority in society. In the developed and developing countries of the world, special attention is paid to informatization of education, ways to develop education and increase its effectiveness are being sought.

The fundamental changes taking place in our society, the practical steps towards the step-by-step transition to an information society, and the extensive reforms being carried out in connection with the integration into the world education system require the wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process. is doing. [1][3][4].

iSpring Quizmaker 8 is a software for creating interactive tests, quizzes and

surveys with functional and at the same time simple-to-use tools. Using **iSpring Quizmaker 8**, you can create 11 different types of tests that determine the knowledge, skills and qualifications of the test taker. It is possible to objectively assess the level of students' mastery of science with the help of questionnaires of 12 different types, which can be enriched with formulas, pictures, audio and video clips.

When the iSpring Suite 8 program tab is activated and the Test section is selected, the following window opens:

Figure 1. Structure of the test section.

From this window, select the "New test" button and the iSpring Quizmaker 8 window will be activated.

Figure 2. The process of selecting test types in iSpring Quizmaker 8.

iSpring Quizmaker 8 includes the following types of assessment tests:

1. **Verno/neverno-** It is done by evaluating the correctness of the assertion.
2. **Oдиночный выбор-** It is done by choosing the correct answer from among the answers.
3. **Mnojestvennyy vybor-** It is done by choosing several correct answers from among the answers.
4. **Vvod stroke** - The answer to the given question is made by entering it in a special field.
5. **Sootvetstvie-** It is carried out by matching the elements of the answer to the elements given in the question.
6. **Order** - It is done by placing the options given in the question in the correct order.
7. **Enter the number** - The correct answer is entered as a number.
8. **Propuski-** One or more omitted sentences from the text of the test task are inserted by the test taker.
9. **Vlojennye otvety** - A complex test form, several questions arranged in the order of "Одиночный выбор" are asked under a single question.
10. **Bank slov-** Several omitted words in the text are selected from the word bank below the text and put in their place.
11. **Aktivnaya oblast** - the area where the answer to the question in the given picture is shown with the help of the mouse.

For example, the picture below shows the test form "Mnojestvennyy vybor" provided by this program, which creates the possibility of choosing several options[2][3][5]. In order to solve the test correctly, it is necessary to quote all the correct answers. If one wrong answer is marked, the test result is considered invalid.

Figure 3. The process of using the "Multiple choice" test type in the iSpring Quizmaker 8 program.

iSpring Quizmaker allows you to create mixed tests using all types of questions.

In the **iSpring Quizmaker** program, multimedia objects are created on the user side, each of the test questions can be filled with pictures, formulas, audio, video or Flash-rolls. In addition, the user can change the text style and set the hyperlink.

Alternatively, answers to tests created in the iSpring Quizmaker program can be filled with pictures and formulas.

iSpring Quizmaker allows you to create branched quizzes. The user can provide specific instructions for correct, incorrect and partially correct answers. If the answer is correct, the student can go to the next question, if the answer is incorrect, he can go to the information slide related to this question. In addition, it is possible to issue a message about the correct or incorrect answer of each test.

Test setup. With **iSpring Quizmaker**, the user can customize the navigation, shuffle questions, select the player, and customize all messages and notes.

With the help of **iSpring Quizmaker**, it is possible to send the complete results of tests and questionnaires to e-mail and to the server. To do this, you need to enter the mail and server address in the test configuration section.

After entering test questions and answers, you can check their final appearance in full form by clicking the "Check it out" button.

Figure 4. A demonstration of a test question created in the " Multiple choice" test type

Saving the test in memory is also done through the " Publication" button.

It is possible to export the tests created in MS Excel to the iSpring Quizmaker program, and this process allows to quickly automate the content of large-scale tests through the program in a short time [2][5][6].

iSpring Suite 8 which is considered one of the authoring software tools, has an extremely easy-to-use interface and provides an opportunity to create interactive electronic content for educators and representatives of various fields.

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